

MONOLOGUE IS A TYPE OF COMMUNICATION

Scientific supervisor: Ph.D., Ganikhanova M. B.

Zilolova Gulhayo Muhammadkarim qizi

Oriental University

Linguistics (English) student

Abstract: *The article discusses the development of the concept of monologic speech and its importance in speech art.*

Keywords: *Speech, monologue, dialogue, conversation, development*

In connected speech, the concept of monologue speech occupies a central place. According to researcher Leontiev, monologue speech has some features:

1. Monologue speech is a type of extended speech, because we are forced not only to name the object, but also to describe it, if the listeners did not know about the previously mentioned topic.

2. Monologue is an optional type of speech. The speaker who wants to express the content should choose an adequate language form for this content and build a speech based on it. The main task of developing coherent speech is to improve monologic speech. In the process of reading and learning children's rhymes and jokes, it is necessary to start developing monologue speech from the age of 2. From the age of 4, children can use such types of monologue as description and narration. It is necessary to form a monologue speech in children from middle age. For older preschoolers, there is a type of monologue - thinking in one or two sentences. The following tasks were set in the formation of monologue speech in children:

1. Development of appropriate monologue speech. Learn to create stories from

toys, pictures, personal and collective experiences.

2. Stimulating and developing speech creativity of children.
3. Developing children's vocabulary by expanding their understanding of social events, people's relationships and character.
4. Maintain interest in the story.
5. Pay special attention to students with speech impediments.
6. Increasing interest in the language and the desire to speak correctly.

The methods of monologue speech are as follows:

1. Retelling. Children repeat monologue texts, talk about real and imaginary events and things.
2. Writing - here children create various creative stories, make up fairy tales independently. Such types of monologic speech are available for children with an average level of development, but children with a low level of development require an individual approach. Various texts are used for this: daily messages transmitted to children in the course of free daily communication with adults; works fiction.

The topics of messages can be different: events, events that happened on the way to work, on a walk, in the forest, in the park, etc., and there can be a description of animals, flowers, some kind of house, tree, forest - one in other words, what surrounds a person. Oral sketches, life events should be expressed correctly and expressively, in a confidential tone, sometimes cheerfully, with humor, because these sketches make a great impression on children. They willingly, with pleasure, tell them to each other, thereby developing direct monologue speech. With preschool children, you can talk about things, events, you can only introduce vocabulary and grammatical forms familiar to children who are formed every day, as a result of which a difficult form of speech - monologue speech develops. A teacher works with children accompanying PMPk preschool according to an

individual program, Retelling works of art is also a way of developing monologue speech. Leading questions help children retell the artwork. At a younger age, the question should be formed from the compound repetition to the last word of the phrase. For example:

Educator: Rooster - rooster, what is gold? What is gold in it?

Child: comb.

Often the teacher should answer the question and have the child repeat the answer. The number of times a work of art should be read depends on how the speech has developed and the level of development of the child. Toddlers need to read the same nursery rhyme five or more times, memorizing individual phrases, before they begin to recognize them. Prompt questions help younger children retell. Starting with young children, repetition should be achieved in repeating individual words and whole phrases, as well as helping to remember the text. Older children should ask direct questions, sometimes using prompts to facilitate verbalization.

For example: in the retelling of L. N. Tolstoy's fairy tale "The Three Bears":

Educator: Where were the bears when Masha wandered into their house?

Child: The bears were not at home, they went for a walk in the forest.

Educator: How many rooms were there in the bear's house?

Child. There were two rooms in the house: one was the dining room and the other was the bedroom. Sometimes the child may skip the last part of the sentence, then the question to be asked should be asked.

Already in middle age, children need to develop the ability to repeat narrative and descriptive works, but the leading form of learning is based on the teacher's questions, oral examples, often accompanied by a didactic game. , or display real objects or images.

References:

1. Babansky Yu.K. Methods of teaching in modern general education school. T.: Teacher, 1990. – 232 p.
2. Ball G.A. Theory uchebnykh zadach: Psychological and pedagogical aspect. M.: Pedagogy, 1990. – 184 p. 120.
3. Bepalko V.P. Slagaemye pedagogical technology. M.: Pedagogy, 1989. – 192 p. Khakimov, S. R., & Sharopov, B. K. (2023). Educational Quality Improvement Events Based on Exhibition Materials in Practical Training Lessons. *American Journal of Language, Literacy and Learning in STEM Education*, 1(2), 5-10.
4. Yuvmitov, A., & Hakimov, S. R. (2021). Influence of seismic isolation on the stress-strain state of buildings. *Acta of Turin Polytechnic University in Tashkent*, 11(1), 71-79.
5. Шаропов, Б. Х., Хакимов, С. Р., & Рахимова, С. (2021). Оптимизация режимов гелиотеплохимической обработки золоцементных композиций. *Матрица научного познания*, (12-1), 115-123.
6. Ювмитов, А. С., & Хакимов, С. Р. (2020). ИССЛЕДОВАНИЕ ВЛИЯНИЯ СЕЙСМОИЗОЛЯЦИИ НА ДИНАМИЧЕСКИЕ ХАРАКТЕРИСТИКИ ЗДАНИЯ. *Acta of Turin Polytechnic University in Tashkent*, 10(2), 14.
7. Hakimov, S., & Dadaxanov, F. (2022). STATE OF HEAT CONDUCTIVITY OF WALLS OF RESIDENTIAL BUILDINGS. *Science and innovation*, 1(C7), 223-226.
8. Yuldashev, S., & Hakimov, S. (2022). ТЕМИР ЙЎЛ ТРАНСПОРТИДАН КЕЛИБ ЧИҚАДИГАН ТЕБРАНИШЛАР ҲАҚИДА. *Science and innovation*, 1(A5), 376-379
9. Хакимов, С. (2022). АКТИВ ВА ПАССИВ СЕЙСМИК УСУЛЛАРИ ҲАМДА УЛАРНИНГ АСОСИЙ ВАЗИФАЛАРИ. *Journal of Integrated Education and Research*, 1(2), 30-36.
10. Khamidov, A. I., & Khakimov, S. (2023). Study of the Properties of Concrete Based on Non-Fired Alkaline Binders. *European Journal of Geography, Regional Planning and Development*, 1(1), 33-39.

- 11.Khamidov, A., & Khakimov, S. (2023). MOISTURE LOSS FROM FRESHLY LAID CONCRETE DEPENDING ON THE TEMPERATURE AND HUMIDITY OF THE ENVIRONMENT. *Science and innovation*, 2(A4), 274-279.